

Social service of the Ukrainian Greek Catholic Church and the Roman Catholic Church in Ukraine in the conditions of the current war of the Russian Federation against Ukraine

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SOCIAL SERVICE OF THE UKRAINIAN CATHOLIC CHURCH AND THE ROMAN CATHOLIC CHURCH IN UKRAINE IN THE CONDITIONS OF THE CURRENT WAR OF THE RBSSIAN FEDERATION AGAINST UKRAINE

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Abstract

The article examines the features of the organization and content of the social work of the Ukrainian Greek Catholic Church (hereinafter – the UGCC) and the Roman Catholic Church in Ukraine (hereinafter – the RCC in Ukraine) during the ongoing war of the Russian Federation against Ukraine. The spheres and accents of the application of social service of these Churches, its performers and beneficiaries, and the features of the implementation of humanitarian charity in wartime are identified. In the UGCC, social work is supervised by its Department of Social Service, in the RCC in Ukraine – by the Caritas-Spes Commission, and the relevant practical activity is carried out mainly through the following Catholic organizations that have their own divisions in both of these Churches: Caritas, the Maltese Aid Service, the Kolping Society, the Community of Saint Egidio, the Knights of Columbus, as well as the St. Martin Foundation (Dominicans). The social service of both Catholic denominations in Ukraine is characterized by systematicity and complexity, a wide coverage of practical areas, close cooperation and exchange of experience between the relevant organizational units of both Churches, which enjoy significant support from international Catholic charitable organizations. In the UGCC and the RCC in Ukraine, the aid is provided not only with “fish”, but also with “fishing rods” (offerings of many educational programs and projects, assistance in employment), as well as - qualified psychological support. The beneficiaries of social assistance are persons who need it, regardless of their denomination. Some of the beneficiaries later become volunteers themselves. Volunteering among the believers of these two Churches and other willing people is encouraged, training of employees and volunteers is carried out. In general, the social work in both of these Churches is intensified in wartime conditions; it is characterized by mobility and rapid adaptation to new needs and tasks. Thus, the UGCC and the RCC in Ukraine demonstrate energetic social service during the war, patriotically responding to the challenges of the day.

Keywords: Ukrainian Greek Catholic Church, Roman Catholic Church in Ukraine, social service, charitable organizations, war.

Introduction

During the ongoing war of the Russian Federation against Ukraine, Ukrainian citizens have intensified mutual assistance. Social service to those in need is carried out by various public organizations and Churches. Such activity is traditional for Churches. In particular, the Ukrainian Greek Catholic Church (hereinafter referred to as the UGCC) and the Roman Catholic Church in Ukraine (hereinafter referred to as the RCC in Ukraine) have accumulated extensive relevant experience, which is very useful during the wartime hardships. There are too many people in need of help in wartime, so the social service of the Churches cannot be overestimated. It is very relevant for religious scholars to study this service, paying attention to the traditional and new aspects of the relevant activity.

Among the already conducted studies, it is worth mentioning the work of O. Vasilyeva and N. Mysak¹, highlighting the participation of the Churches in solving urgent social problems in Ukraine, the articles of S. Filipchuk² and O. Nedavnya³, who analyzed social work in the modern UGCC, and the article of T. Gavryliuk and M. Lukashenko⁴, who analyzed such work in the modern RCC in Ukraine. S. Babynska⁵ and O. Kolomyychuk⁶ paid attention to the social projects of Caritas

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- 1 Васильєва, О., Мисак, Н. Участь церкви у вирішенні актуальних суспільних проблем України. *Науковий щорічник "Історія релігій в Україні"*. 2014. № 24-2: Випуск 24, Книга II. 206-211. <https://religio.org.ua/index.php/religio/article/view/710/709>. [Vasilyeva, O., Mysak, N. The participation of the church in solving current social problems of Ukraine. *Scientific yearbook "History of religions in Ukraine"*]
 - 2 Fylypchuk, S. Special spheres of the UGCC charitable activity in the light of confessional media: religious analysis. *Skhid*, 2019. 1(159), 95–98. [https://doi.org/10.21847/1728-9343.2019.1\(159\).157939](https://doi.org/10.21847/1728-9343.2019.1(159).157939)
 - 3 Недавня, Ольга. Трансформації в Українській Греко-Католицькій Церкві у добу сучасних георелігійних процесів та культурно-цивілізаційних зрушень (за період війни 2014-2022 рр.) *Георелігійні процеси і конфесійні трансформації в Україні: колективна монографія / За заг. ред. О.Сагана. К.: Світ Знань, 2023. 252-259.* <https://drive.google.com/file/d/1AzLHTYzmJEeUZmpBNUqO9vsXRqZzXfW5/view?fbclid=IwAR2lXrQLS7zGl64bhDoVtz9wWYixSnDOErDfXsXA-J78p5YV47EXkxvsU30&pli=1>. [Nedavnya, Olga. Transformations in the Ukrainian Greek Catholic Church in the Age of Modern Georeligious Processes and Cultural and Civilizational Changes (for the War Period 2014-2022). *Georeligious Processes and Confessional Transformations in Ukraine: Collective Monograph / Edited by O. Sagan. Kyiv: World of Knowledge*]
 - 4 Havryliuk, Tetiana and Lukashenko, Maryna. Roman Catholicism in Ukraine: The Contemporary Situation, Social Acceptance, and Social Service. *Occasional Papers on Religion in Eastern Europe*: 2020. Vol. 40: Iss. 3, Article 5. <https://digitalcommons.georgefox.edu/ree/vol40/iss3/5>
 - 5 Бабинська, С. Південний форпост "Карітасу" УГКЦ. *Патріархат*. 11.09.2023. <https://www.patriyarkhat.org.ua/statti-zhurnalu/pivdennyy-forpost-karitasu-uhkts/>. [Babynska, S. Southern outpost of "Caritas" of the UGCC. *Patriarchate*]
 - 6 Коломийчук, Олександр. Caritas у воєнний час: особливості діяльності місцевих БО "Карітас" у справі адаптації вимушених переселенців на Прикарпатті (2022–2024). Тези Міжнародної науково-практичної конференції "Збереження національної спадщини та розвиток культурних практик в умовах суспільних викликів" (Київ, 19–20 березня 2017 року)/ ІМФЕ ім.М.Т.Рильського НАН України. Київ, 2025. 147-150.

in their works. However, there is currently a lack of a comprehensive analysis of this topic in both of these Churches, which have many common projects, approaches and features. Therefore, the purpose of this article is to determine the specifics of the organization and content of the social work of the UGCC and the RCC in Ukraine during the modern war, for which it is necessary to identify areas and accents of the application of the social service by these Churches, its executants and beneficiaries, and the features of the implementation of humanitarian charity in wartime circumstances.

The Main Material and Results

In the UGCC, the social work is supervised by the Department of Social Service, which is an advisory and coordinating body under the Synod of Bishops of the UGCC and the Head of the UGCC in the field of social service, which is carried out by the structures of the UGCC and with its support. This Church defines social service as an activity aimed at solving social problems and ensuring social justice. Such work covers the entire spectrum of social activity, including the provision of volunteer assistance, charity, organized forms of offering social services to individuals and groups in need.⁷ The Department of Social Service determines strategic goals of the development of various areas of this activity, provides general supervision, monitoring and coordination of interaction between the structures of the UGCC that carry out social service, and also represents the social service of the UGCC in general public and interfaith processes.

In the RCC in Ukraine, social service is handled by the Caritas-Spes Commission, which has similar goals and objectives.⁸ This Commission operates under the Bishops' Conference of Ukraine, in cooperation with other Commissions, in particular: the Commission for Integral Human Development, the Commission for Church Movements and Communities, etc. It is noticeable how this Church emphasizes charity. Along with accentuation that Christ taught to support the poor, to show mercy to the offended and needy, it is emphasized that Jesus “does not exalt economic poverty and does not demonize wealth. He focuses on ensuring that a person does not attach his heart to material things, does not put in first place goods that can be purchased for money. The material resources that a Christian has during his earthly life should serve God's purposes, deeds of mercy.”⁹

The full-scale phase of the Russian Federation's war against Ukraine expanded the needs of social service, which prompted to rethinking them and to new approaches in social work. Therefore, in September 2022, the UGCC adopted the Strategy for the Development of Social Service¹⁰. This document formulates the main areas of effort to develop the ability of the UGCC to provide a worthy

<https://www.etnolog.org.ua/pdf/stories/zbirnyky/2025/tezy.pdf>. [Kolomyychuk, Oleksandr. Caritas in wartime: features of the activities of local Caritas organizations in the adaptation of internally displaced persons in the Carpathian region (2022–2024). *Abstracts of the International Scientific and Practical Conference “Preservation of National Heritage and Development of Cultural Practices in Conditions of Social Challenges”* (Kyiv, March 19–20, 2017) / M.T. Rylsky Institute of Cultural Heritage of the NAS of Ukraine]

7 Відділ соціального служіння УГКЦ. *Українська Греко-Католицька Церква*. <https://ugcc.ua/curia/pastoral-council/department-of-social-service/>. [Department of Social Service of the UGCC. *Ukrainian Greek Catholic Church*]

8 Комісії. *Римсько-Католицька Церква в Україні*. <https://rkc.org.ua/konferentsiya-yepuskopiv/komisiyi/>. [Commissions. *Roman Catholic Church in Ukraine*]

9 Благодійність. *Римсько-Католицька Церква в Україні*. <https://rkc.org.ua/blagodijnist/>. [Charity. *Roman Catholic Church in Ukraine*]

10 Стратегія розвитку соціального служіння УГКЦ. *Офіційні документи Української Греко-Католицької Церкви*. 9.09.2022. <https://docs.ugcc.ua/1598/>. [Strategy for the Development of Social Service of the UGCC. *Official Documents of the Ukrainian Greek Catholic Church*]

response to existing and future social challenges, and to increase the role of the UGCC in spreading Christian values among society, communities, families and individuals. The Strategy for Social Service of the UGCC has the following priority goals: fostering the spirit of sacrifice and social responsibility, serving for the benefit of those in need, and institutional development and professionalization of social service of the UGCC. It should be noted that the latter is especially relevant in a situation where wartime circumstances stimulate the clergy and laity involved to master new areas of social service, new skills.

The RCC in Ukraine also focused on current changes in social service in 2022. At the 57th plenary session of the Conference of Roman Catholic Bishops, the Executive Director of Caritas-Spes Ukraine, Fr. Vyacheslav Hrynevych SAC, presented the mission's activities since the beginning of the full-scale war in Ukraine and the gestures of support from the international community. A meeting was previously held with representatives of the Pontifical Foundation "Aid to the Church in Need" in order to clarify the urgent needs of Ukrainians and the Church, so that more effective assistance could be provided.¹¹

Over the past three years of full-scale war, the UGCC and the RCC in Ukraine have gained new experience in social service, mastering both its purely church areas and areas where the efforts of the Churches and secular factors meet or coexist. This is military chaplaincy at the front and in the rear, psychological assistance to fellow citizens in trouble, grief, hardship, and stress. The UGCC and the RCC in Ukraine are working on such experience, sharing it with each other, and determining the further development of social service. Thus, the Synod of Bishops of the UGCC in 2024 analyzed the social activity of the Church during the war. It was presented by Bishop Vasyl Tuchapets, head of the Department of Social Service, in his report. Patriarchal Economist Fr. Lubomyr Yavorsky presented the projects implemented on behalf of the Church by the Patriarchal Foundation "Mudra Sprava"; Director of the International Charitable Foundation "Caritas Ukraine" Tetiana Stavnycha reported on the areas of activity of the Foundation, Sister Sevastiyana Karvatska, OSBM, informed the bishops about the status of the implementation of the church program for the clergy of the UGCC "Healing the Wounds of War". The Synod determined that serving fellow citizens suffering from Russian aggression, supporting the most vulnerable segments of Ukrainian society, and working to heal the wounds of war would remain priorities in the service of the Church in the coming years and further perspective.¹²

Similarly, the RCC in Ukraine is working on the war experience of its social work and relevant cooperation. At their 2024 plenary session, the bishops of the RCC in Ukraine discussed charity matters and met with representatives of the charitable organizations Renovabis, Help to the Church in needs and the Weltkirche/Weltmission Section of the Cologne Archdiocese. Partners from abroad presented the bishops with proposals for further cooperation and the implementation of charitable projects. The Religious Mission "Caritas-Spes Ukraine" presented a report on implemented projects and information on current challenges. The bishops expressed gratitude to all charitable organiza-

11 Комюніке 57 пленарного засідання Конференції римсько-католицьких єпископів в Україні. *Римсько-Католицька Церква в Україні*. 25.11.2022. <https://rkcs.org.ua/blog/2022/11/25/komyunike-57-go-plenarnogo-zasidannya-konferencziyi-rymsko-katolyckyyh-yepyskopiv-v-ukrayini/>. [Communiqué of the 57th plenary session of the Conference of Roman Catholic Bishops in Ukraine. *Roman Catholic Church in Ukraine*]

12 Комунікат Синоду Єпископів Української Греко-Католицької Церкви. *Офіційні документи Української Греко-Католицької Церкви*. 15.07.2024. <https://docs.ugcc.ua/1746/>. [Communiqué of the Synod of Bishops of the Ukrainian Greek Catholic Church. *Official documents of the Ukrainian Greek Catholic Church*]

tions and their partners for comprehensive assistance to those in need: internally displaced persons, low-income families, as well as people who lost their homes and property as a result of hostilities.¹³ The bishops of the RCC in Ukraine approved the components of the development plan for the Church in Ukraine for the nearest period. They ask believers to continue joint prayers and care for those who physically, materially or spiritually suffer from hostilities. The bishops especially encourage “support both prayerfully and materially for our soldiers – sons and daughters of our Motherland who are currently at the front, as well as those who have lost their health, suffered serious injuries or lost limbs as a result of hostilities, and their families.”¹⁴

Practical work of social service is carried out by a number of Catholic organizations. The most powerful of them is Caritas. This is an international charitable Foundation, which has over 115 years of history and unites 165 national organizations in 200 countries of the world, with a staff of several million employees and volunteers.¹⁵ The mission of Caritas is developing traditions of charity and carrying out social work, based on Christian moral and ethical values. Local branches of “Caritas” work in different countries and in different Catholic Churches (of Latin and Eastern rites). In Ukraine, these are Caritas-Ukraine UGCC (actually operating since 1992, officially registered — in 1999.¹⁶ and Caritas-Spes RCC in Ukraine (actually operating since 1990, registration completed in 1996).¹⁷ Numerous Greek and Roman Catholic volunteers work in Caritas of the UGCC and the RCC in Ukraine.

Caritas Ukraine currently has over 40 regional organizations in 20 regions of our country and over a thousand employees and volunteers.¹⁸ The Caritas-Spes Religious Mission of the RCC in Ukraine works in all Ukrainian regions. It has a National Office and seven regional centers operating in each diocese of this Church and numbering about 800 employees and volunteers.¹⁹

Caritas is characterized by a comprehensive and systematic approach to solving social issues (taking into account their totality, sequence and potential consequences) and scientific approaches in social work, its own research of the problems of medicine, migration, unemployment, homelessness, orphanhood and street lifestyle of children and youth, integration of people with disabilities, etc. Caritas employees are characterized by high qualifications and continuous professional development through participation in their own and partners’ trainings, seminars, conferences, internships in Ukraine and abroad.²⁰

13 Комюніке 61 пленарного засідання єпископату. *Римсько-Католицька Церква в Україні*. 30.11.2024. <https://rkc.org.ua/blog/2024/11/30/комунике-61-plenarnogo-zasidannya-uepyskopatu/>. [Communiqué of the 61st plenary session of the Episcopate. *Roman Catholic Church in Ukraine*]

14 Комюніке 61 пленарного засідання єпископату. *Римсько-Католицька Церква в Україні*. 30.11.2024. <https://rkc.org.ua/blog/2024/11/30/комунике-61-plenarnogo-zasidannya-uepyskopatu/>. [Communiqué of the 61st plenary session of the Episcopate. *Roman Catholic Church in Ukraine*]

15 Карітас в Україні. *Карітас України*. <https://caritas.ua/about/>. [Caritas in Ukraine. *Caritas Ukraine*]

16 Карітас в Україні. *Карітас України*. <https://caritas.ua/about/>. [Caritas in Ukraine. *Caritas Ukraine*]

17 Історія створення “Карітас-Спес” в Україні. *Карітас-Спес Україна*. <https://caritas-spes.org.ua/page/who-we-are/istorija-stvorennja-karitasspes-v-ukraini>. [The history of the creation of “Caritas-Spes” in Ukraine. *Caritas-Spes Ukraine*]

18 Карітас в Україні. *Карітас України*. <https://caritas.ua/about/>. [Caritas in Ukraine. *Caritas Ukraine*]

19 Про нас. *Карітас-Спес Україна*. <https://caritas-spes.org.ua/page/who-we-are/about-us>. [About us. *Caritas-Spes Ukraine*]

20 Карітас в Україні. *Карітас України*. <https://caritas.ua/about/>. [Caritas in Ukraine. *Caritas*

Caritas' work is traditionally focused on the following main areas: assistance to socially vulnerable children, youth and families in crisis; healthcare; support for the elderly people and people with special needs; social problems of migration; assistance in emergency situations. All this assistance is provided to those in need, regardless of their religion or denomination. In Ukraine, even before the full-scale invasion of the Russian Federation, Caritas also focused on community development programs and support for social entrepreneurship, which was and is especially relevant in a country with a post-socialist and post-colonial legacy. In addition to effective and practical social and material assistance, which is especially necessary in wartime conditions, Caritas conducts active educational and training work. The various directions of the relevant work are evidenced by the completed and ongoing projects of Caritas Ukraine²¹ and Caritas-Spes.²²

It should also be added that Caritas practices long-term partnership with both Ukrainian and international charitable foundations and public organizations, and state structures.

Socially-oriented support and assistance are also provided by Ukrainian branches of other international Catholic organizations, whose activities are aimed, in particular, at social and humanitarian service. The members of such branches are, in the absolute majority, the believers of the UGCC and the RCC in Ukraine.

Since the Revolution of Dignity on the Maidan, the second such organization that has become widely known to Ukrainians is the Maltese Aid Service (hereinafter — MAS). It began its work in Ukraine in December 1990. in Lviv, as part of winter humanitarian aid from Germany, and on February 23, 1993, at the initiative of the Sovereign Military Order of Malta and the German Maltese Aid Service, the charitable organization “Maltese Aid Service in Lviv” was registered. Almost simultaneously, a MAS center was founded in Ivano-Frankivsk, later in Beregovo and Mukachevo (Transcarpathia), and in the capital of Ukraine. In 2013, these centers merged into the Maltese Aid Service of Ukraine. The main areas of activity of the MAS are assistance to children in need, low-income elderly people in need, people with disabilities, displaced persons, children and mothers in crisis situations. The first project of the MAS was a charity kitchen. For its visitors, who are mainly low-income single elderly people in need, a Christmas dinner and an Easter breakfast are organized every year. In 2007, the MAS's project “Kitchen on Wheels” – delivering hot meals to those in need and with limited mobility – was launched.²³

MAS helps boarding schools and orphanages to solve many urgent needs. These include repairing their premises, providing them with educational equipment and supplies, equipping dental offices and sports training facilities, educational workshops and libraries. MAS also provides gifts to children from boarding schools and orphanages, in particular as part of the annual campaign “Saint Nicholas – for children in need”). MAS also implements educational and cultural programs.²⁴ It is worth noting that MAS gives priority to projects that are “Help for self-help” in nature: giving not only “a fish”, but also “a fishing rod” (tractor, apiary, sewing workshop, carpentry workshop, bicycle workshop). This approach is constructive at any time, and in wartime it is especially appropriate.

Ukraine]

21 Діяльність. *Карітас України*. <https://caritas.ua/diyalnist/>. [Activities. *Caritas Ukraine*]

22 Діючі проєкти. *Карітас-Спес Україна*. <https://caritas-spes.org/ua/page/dijuchi-proekti>. [Current projects. *Caritas-Spes Ukraine*]; Завершені проєкти. *Карітас-Спес Україна*. <https://caritas-spes.org/ua/page/zaversheni-proekti>. [Completed projects. *Caritas-Spes Ukraine*]

23 Про нас. *Мальтійська служба допомоги*. <https://malteser.ua/about/>. [About us. *Maltese Aid Service*]

24 Допомога дітям. *Мальтійська служба допомоги*. <https://malteser.ua/help/>. [Help for children. *Maltese Aid Service*]

Also, in wartime, such a direction of MAS's work with children as the “Mobile Play Space” project became especially relevant. It is an initiative designed to give children happy moments of childhood, even in the most difficult times. This project was created so that children could feel joy, restore emotional balance and evolve, despite the difficulties of war. MAS employees arrange a mobile play space in shelters, schools, kindergartens and orphanages for children who are most in need of comfort, who find themselves in difficult life circumstances or are experiencing the consequences of war.²⁵

For over 15 years, MAS has been providing social services to people with disabilities who use wheelchairs: in addition to daily work on the social and psychological adaptation of people with disabilities, there are annual summer camps for them and pilgrimages to holy spots in Ukraine and abroad. In 2009, MAS launched a support program for family-type orphanages and cooperation with centers for large families and several crisis centers for mothers with children. MAS has experience in successfully conducting large-scale campaigns in other areas of assistance to those in need: providing assistance to flood victims in Transcarpathia, purchasing medical equipment for surgical operations on newborns under artificial blood circulation, training in providing first medical aid, etc.²⁶

Like Caritas, MAS fosters volunteerism. MAS conducts projects for education and formation of volunteer youth. Since 1995, MAS is a co-organizer of the annual May youth walking pilgrimage to the Holy Dormition Univ Lavra. People with disabilities also join the pilgrimage.²⁷

During the war, MAS focuses its efforts on humanitarian, social, and psychological assistance to victims, which includes the rehabilitation of wounded soldiers, ensuring the basic needs of refugees in temporary shelters, humanitarian and medical support for the civilian population in need. Since the beginning of the full-scale invasion of the Russian Federation into Ukraine, MAS has been feeding refugees at the Main Railway Station and Bus Station in Lviv, helping them in queues at the borders, and providing logistics for humanitarian aid from abroad through the representative offices of the Order of Malta and the Maltese World Services. MAS has also organized courses in providing first pre-medical aid and continues to provide food to the elderly people²⁸. During the war with its stresses, horrors and troubles, the MAS intensified psychological assistance, in particular at the Center for Psychological Guidance and Support.²⁹

A number of other Catholic organizations engaged in social work found their sympathizers in Ukraine among Greek and Roman Catholics who provide social service for their fellow citizens. These are the Kolping Society, the Knights of Columbus, the St. Martin Foundation, the Community of St. Egidius, etc.

“The Kolping Society in Ukraine” has been operating for 25 years, is registered as a public organization for social support of citizens and is part of the global Kolping “family”. Its first center was “The Kolping Family of Chernivtsi”. The Kolping Society has united Roman and Greek

25 Мобільний ігровий простір Мальтійської служби допомоги. *Мальтійська служба допомоги*. 10.12.2023. <https://malteser.ua/2023/12/10/mobilniy-igroviy-prostir-dlya-ditey/>. [Malta Aid Service mobile gaming space. *Malta Aid Service*]

26 Про нас. *Мальтійська служба допомоги*. <https://malteser.ua/about/>. [About us. *Maltese Aid Service*]

27 Про нас. *Мальтійська служба допомоги*. <https://malteser.ua/about/>. [About us. *Maltese Aid Service*]

28 Допомога в умовах війни в Україні. *Мальтійська служба допомоги*. <https://malteser.ua/about/>. [Aid in conditions of the war in Ukraine. *Maltese Aid Service*]

29 Наша діяльність. *Мальтійська служба допомоги*. <https://malteser.ua/#activity>. [Our activities. *Maltese Aid Service*]

Catholics in its activities, although anyone can work in it, and this organization, like Caritas, MAS and others, helps people of different denominations, being an open and ecumenical structure. The Kolping Society has been helping displaced people since 2014, but mainly in their socialization: legal support, consultations, support in employment. The full-scale invasion added work for them: the social kitchen for internally displaced persons expanded, and it was necessary to start working on the arrangement of shelters for them. The Kolping Society also supports fighters on the front line - with generators, warm clothing, food, etc.³⁰

The history of the Knights of Columbus in our country dates back to 2012, when the Head of the UGCC Svyatoslav Shevchuk and the Head of the Conference of the Roman Catholic Bishops of Ukraine Mechislav Mokshitzky became its first knights in Ukraine. This fraternal organization of Catholic men is not only charitable, but charity is a component of its activities and is defined as a key part of its mission. The Knights of Columbus are engaged in charity on the principle of implementing it at home, with families, in their local communities. During the war, this means a whole range of assistance, because in many Ukrainian families there are soldiers at the front, wounded soldiers, relatives of dead or captured soldiers, and in many Ukrainian communities there are forcibly displaced persons.³¹

The Catholic organization that deals, in particular, with humanitarian aid is the Community of Saint Egidius. It has been operating in Ukraine since 1991, providing humanitarian aid to people in difficult life circumstances, internally displaced persons, the elderly and the homeless people, and children. In 1999, this organization launched a program of long-distance care for children living in boarding schools or family-type homes. Since the beginning of the full-scale military invasion of the Russian Federation into Ukraine, the Community of Saint Egidius has been providing assistance to medical institutions throughout the country, as well as to local administrations and communities in front-line regions. It operates 4 humanitarian centers where internally displaced persons receive humanitarian aid: in Lviv, Ivano-Frankivsk, and two centers in Kyiv. Every month, these centers distribute about 12,000 food packages to those in need. Such aid centers are also integration tools: people who come as beneficiaries start volunteering, find friends. Young people in the Community of Saint Egidio help the homeless and the elderly people on a volunteer basis. In addition to those included in the distance care program, the Community has supported and provided humanitarian assistance to thousands of minors in Ukraine, with whom it has contacted in children's institutions, pediatric centers and hospitals, and refugee centers.³²

Like the Maltese Aid Service at one time, the St. Martin Foundation was founded on the initiative of representatives of the Catholic order - through the efforts of the Dominicans, who

30 Об'єдналися на благодійному фронті: як працює “Справа Кольпінга” під час війни. *Media-грамотність у регіонах України*. 9.12.2023. <https://milukraine.net/2023/12/obyednalys-na-blagodijnomu-fronti/>. [United on the charitable front: how the “Kolping case” works during the war. *Media literacy in the regions of Ukraine*]

31 Програми: громада. *Лицарі Колумба. Національна рада*. 23.02.2019. <https://lytsarikolumba.com/prohramy-hromada/>. [Programs: Community. *Knights of Columbus. National Council*]

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involved both volunteers and the support of foreign philanthropists in the cause of helping orphans and frail elderly people. This charitable organization was established in Ukraine in 2005, and even before the start of the Russian war against Ukraine, it launched energetic activities in matters of social service: from charity kitchens and humanitarian aid with clothing, medicine and household items to educational, cultural, sports and recreational programs, etc. A few days before the full-scale invasion of the Russian Federation troops, the St. Martin Foundation adopted the Strategy of the St. Martin House in Difficult Times³³, and at the same time, this house accepted 40 children from Mariupol, who were saved at the last moment, as part of the ongoing project "Rehabilitation of Children of the Gray Zone". The St. Martin Foundation has been implementing this project since 2016, and with the beginning of the full-scale phase of the war, the St. Martin House opened a mobile shelter and began a humanitarian mission aimed at supporting and effectively assisting the victims of the war. In February 2022 hundreds of people who fled from the north of Kyiv region spent the night there, and not a single day since then has humanitarian aid, psychological support, and numerous social services for the victims stopped.³⁴

Conclusions

So, social service in the UGCC and the RCC in Ukraine during the ongoing war of the Russian Federation against our state is characterized by the following:

- proven organization, systematicity, comprehensiveness, and a wide coverage of practical areas;
- close cooperation and exchange of experience between the relevant organizational units of both these Churches;
- use of significant support from international Catholic charitable organizations;
- emphasis on assistance not only with “fish”, but also with “fishing rods”, offers of many educational programs and projects, assistance in employment;
- qualified psychological support;
- beneficiaries of social assistance are persons who need it, regardless of their denomination;
- encouraging volunteerism among Greek, Roman Catholics and other interested parties, training of employees and volunteers;
- intensification of social work in wartime conditions, its mobility and rapid adaptation to new needs and tasks.

Thus, it can be stated with confidence that the Ukrainian Greek Catholic Church and the Roman Catholic Church in Ukraine demonstrate energetic social service during the war, patriotically responding to contemporary challenges. In a detailed study of the social work of these Churches, it is worth conducting a comparative analysis of such activity among all Churches and religious organizations operating in Ukraine, clarifying its regional features and expected prospects.

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